

Proposed Marketing Strategy to Increase Brand Awareness of Inagri

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ABSTRACT: The technological developments, population growth and the food needs of the Indonesian people in consuming food. Online grocery stores are growing to meet people's needs in the digital era. That is what makes INAGRI as an online grocery sales company continue to innovate in agriculture. Starting to change online shopping behavior can be a huge potential market, but INAGRI faces many people who don't know the INAGRI brand as an online grocery store company, so INAGRI's sales have not reached the target. Therefore, what factors influence someone to know brand awareness really needs to be known. To create a successful marketing strategy, companies must analyze business problems with internal and external environmental analysis. External environment analysis consisting of; PESTEL (Politics, Economics, Social and Technology, Environment, Law), Porter 5 strengths, competitor analysis and consumer analysis using questionnaires and internal focus analysis on the marketing mix known as the 4P marketing mix and STP (Segmenting, Targeting and Positioning). The root cause of the problem says that brand awareness is not high enough, so purchase intention is also not high enough. This research is a quantitative study using Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Model (PLS-SEM) data analysis with the help of Smart PLS 4.0 software. Primary data was obtained from distributing questionnaires to 220 respondents. The results of data processing show that the variables Sales promotion, advertising, brand interactivity have a positive effect on brand awareness. Only content quality has no effect, then brand awareness also has a positive effect on purchase intention. Recommended marketing strategy recommendations are Providing product promotions with brand interactivity and creative advertising, collaborating with influencers, optimizing and making Video TikTok and Instagram sales marketing through social media, participating in marketing events to increase brand awareness and improve the quality of human resources by attending training digital marketing for INAGRI employees.

KEYWORDS: Advertising, Brand Awareness, Marketing Strategy, Purchase Intention, Sales Promotion.

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is dubbed as an Agrarian Country because of its vast agricultural land and abundant natural resources. Agriculture and animal husbandry are sectors that must be focused on because they are related to the country's food needs. The agricultural and livestock sectors have an important role in the Indonesian economy because they contribute to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) [1]. The population of Indonesia continues to increase to 275.77 million people in 2022. This data has increased by 1.13% from the previous year [2]. With a large population, the more food needs from agriculture and agriculture must be met. Internet and technology are two very important things in this day and age. Almost everyone uses the internet almost every day to support and assist daily activities such as work, study, and shopping. With technology, everything that is done can be easier and more practical. Product information from advertising can be obtained quickly from social media. Based on the data about Weekly online shopping activities, ordered groceries via online stores is ranked 2nd highest with 36%. This data describes that online business in the wholesale sector has great opportunities along with the rapid development of technology. This creates opportunities and potential for the business market to carry out several strategies [3]. Based on the company's sales data, the decline in sales that occurred significantly became a business problem and affected the progress of the company. They only experience very strong sales in March and July 2021, and in other months they struggle to meet their sales goals. Based on these conditions, Inagri has a product sales performance declines problem and then Inagri is still lack of brand awareness and lack of purchase intention from the buyers to buy the product. Thus, the purpose of this research is to explore the variables that can prevent a company from achieving its sales goals and recommend a marketing plan, such as brand awareness, that can help businesses increase sales.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Advertising is one part of marketing to attract customer attention to the products being sold so that they are then purchased. Sales promotion is a short-term incentive to encourage product purchases or sales [4]. Sales promotion can include demonstrations in

stores, displays, sales, and loyalty programs. Good advertising messages and content are essential in today's costly and cluttered advertising environment and also because in this era consumers are bombarded with advertisements and brand content at home, office and all points of view [4]. Brand Interactivity is defined as the assistance offered to customers on social media as well as a space for discussion and exchange of ideas, social media brand interactions fundamentally change the communication between brands and customers [5]. A powerful brand enjoys high levels of consumer brand awareness and loyalty [4]. That is why brand awareness is very important in developing a business. Companies must manage their brands carefully. First, the brand's positioning must be continuously communicated to consumers. Major brand marketers often spend huge amounts on advertising to create brand awareness and build preference and loyalty [4]. Purchase Intention is a plan that is planned by consumers to buy a product. Generally, the consumer's purchase decision will be to buy the most preferred brand, but two factors can come between the purchase intention and the purchase decision [4]. Marketing as a process by which companies engage customers, build strong customer relationships, and create customer value to capture value from customers in return for loyalty [4]. Selling and advertising are only part of a larger marketing mix, a set of marketing tools that work together to engage customers, satisfy customer needs and build customer relationships [4].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research starts from problem identification, namely business problems in Inagri and then becomes a research objective arranged in chapter 1. In this research, the author has conducted preliminary research to help with business problems in this research to potential customers and conducted interviews with the Chief Operation Officers and Chief Executive Officers of the company. Based on the preliminary research conducted, the authors developed the conceptual framework in chapter 2 of this study. This research stage was continued with research and literature review searches related to business problems at Inagri and then collecting data to obtain data. This study describes external and internal conditions from 2 different perspectives. External analysis was carried out by analyzing the 5 porter strengths, PESTEL Analysis, Competitor Analysis and Customer Analysis. Then the author will analyze Internal analysis by conducting analysis on VRIO Analysis, Marketing Mix and STP (Segmenting, Targeting and Positioning) Analysis. So that the authors can explain the data and business conditions in the internal analysis and the impact on business from external analysis. After conducting external and internal analysis, the authors conducted a SWOT analysis to analyze the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats of the companies studied. After that the author will provide the right business solution with TOWS Matrix based on the results of the analysis obtained. In the final stage, the author will provide an implementation plan, conclusion and recommendations so that the INAGRI business is being run to grow for the better. Then the author also explains the quantitative method used in this study. After that the author also explained about the tools used when getting data from this study, namely PLS-SEM.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Customer Analysis

1) R-Square

An indicator of how much an exogenous construct can explain an endogenous construct is the coefficient of determination (R Square). The value of the coefficient of determination (R Square) is expected to be between 0 and 1.

Table 1. R table

	R-Square	R-square adjusted
Brand Awareness	0.488	0.478
Purchase Intention	0.350	0.347

The R Square value of the joint or simultaneous influence of Advertising, Sales Promotion, Brand Interactivity, Content Quality on Brand Awareness is 0.488 with an adjusted r square value of 0.478. Thus, it can be explained that all exogenous constructs simultaneously affect other by 0.478 or 47.8%. Because Adjusted R Square is more than 33%, the effect of all exogenous constructs on Brand Awareness is moderate. The R Square value of the simultaneous influence of Advertising,

Sales Promotion, Brand Interactivity, Content Quality, Brand Awareness on Purchase Intention is 0.350 with an adjusted r squared value of 0.347. It can be explained that all exogenous simultaneously affect buying interest by 0.347 or 34.7%. Since Adjusted R Square is more than 33% but less than 67%, the influence of all exogenous constructs of Advertising, Sales Promotion, Brand Interactivity, Content Quality, Brand Awareness on Purchase Intention is moderate.

2) T-Statistics and P-Values

Table 2. T-Statistics and P-Values (SmartPLS,2022)

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T statistics ((O/STDEV))	P values
Advertising -> Brand Awareness	0.413	0.410	0.063	6.517	0.000
Brand Awareness -> Purchase Intention	0.591	0.596	0.054	11.036	0.000
Brand Interactivity -> Brand Awareness	0.214	0.215	0.055	3.907	0.000
Content Quality -> Brand Awareness	-0.006	-0.011	0.069	0.093	0.926
Sales Promotion -> Brand Awareness	0.244	0.256	0.082	2.983	0.003

Based on the table, we can see that from the data obtained there are four data that have statistics above 1.96 and only content quality data on brand awareness which has a t statistic below 1.96 according to the data obtained. The significance of the relationship between can also be assessed between the P values in addition to the t statistic. If the P-value is more than 0.05, the hypothesis cannot be accepted and has no positive effect between the two variables. Based on the data obtained, the association between content quality and brand awareness has a P-Value higher than 0.05.

Table 3. Hypothesis Table (SmartPLS,2022)

Hypothesis	P - Value	Conclusion
H1: Content quality has a positive effect on Brand Awareness.	Rejected	Content quality does not have a positive effect on Brand Awareness
H2: Brand Interactivity has positive effect on Brand Awareness.	Accepted	Brand Interactivity has a positive effect on Brand Awareness
H3: Advertising has positive effect on Brand Awareness.	Accepted	Advertising has a positive effect on Brand Awareness
H4: Sales Promotion has positive effect on Brand Awareness.	Accepted	Sales Promotion has a positive effect on Brand Awareness
H5: Brand Awareness has positive effect on Purchase Intention.	Accepted	Brand Awareness has a positive effect on Purchase intention

B. SWOT Analysis

• Strength (Internal Analysis)

- 1) Has a customer loyalty program by getting a bonus class about business from the Insan Academy
- 2) Offers high quality, new innovations, and unique product
- 3) Affordable Price
- 4) Has SIMTANI COOP (Tani Cooperative System), which is an Agricultural Cooperative Management Information System

- Weakness (Internal Analysis)
 - 1) Lack of promotion activity
 - 2) The use of social media is not optimal
 - 3) Lack of Advertising the product
- Opportunities (External Analysis)
 - 1) There is a Government Policy in the Agriculture and Online Grocery Industry Sector
 - 2) Socio Cultural trends for buy online grocery are in High Demand 3) Increasing Internet users over time
- Threats (External Analysis)
 - 1) Threat of New Entrants
 - 2) Rivalry Among Existing Competitors
 - 3) High Power of Buyers

C. *TOWS Analysis*

- S-O Strategy
 - 1) Give Promotion product with brand interactivity and creative advertising (S1,S2,O2,O3)
 - 2) Collaborate with Influencer to promote Inagri (S2,S3,S4,O1,O2,O3)
- W-O Strategy
 - 1) Give Promotion product with brand interactivity and creative advertising (W1,W2,W3,O2, O3)
 - 2) Optimizing and Creating Video Tiktok and Instagram as a sales marketing social media for advertising and sales promotion (W2,W3,O2,O3)
- S-T Strategy
 - 1) Participating in marketing events to raise brand awareness for Inagri's Innovation (S1,S2,S3,T1,T2,T3)
- W-T Strategy
 - 1) Optimizing and Creating Video Tiktok and Instagram as a sales marketing social media for advertising and sales promotion (W1,W2,W3, T3)
 - 2) Improving the quality of human resource by taking courses on Digital Marketing (W1,W2,W3,T1,T2)

D. *Marketing Strategy*

- Give Promotion product with brand interactivity and creative advertising (SO1, WO1)

Based on previous preliminary interviews in Chapter 1, many respondents answered that brand interactivity is an important factor in increasing brand awareness and then becoming purchase intention. Promotion of creative products and advertisements on Inagri's social media accounts will increase the existence of the Inagri Brand and attract the attention of Inagri's marketing targets because there are many promotions in it. Inagri can carry out promotions with empathy and focus on customer oriented, by conducting brand interaction and building communication and feedback from every customer who buys and is interested in Inagri products, then Inagri can post creative advertisements every week which has the potential to increase Inagri's brand awareness.
- Collaborate with Influencer to promote INAGRI (SO2)

Collaborating with influencers is very important in this digital era. When a business wants to be able to adapt and be agile in the right way, Inagri must be able to adjust to what is trending in today's society. Working with influencers is a way to accelerate the increase in Brand Awareness of a brand, such as a SayurBox that has collaborated with Influence Pupu Paula and can increase the attention of the public who see the content. INAGRI through its Chief Executive Officer can collaborate with one of the Influencers in Indonesia seperti Fiksi aunurofik as a Youtuber, Instagram and Tiktok content creator with 1 million subscribers to help promote Inagri products. With this cooperation and increased public attention, this strategy can have high potential to increase brand awareness of INAGRI products.

- Optimizing and Creating Video Tiktok and Instagram as a sales marketing social media for advertising and sales promotion (WO2)
Tiktok and Instagram reels in 2022 are trending and growing rapidly in society. There is already a lot of content with various types of focus on Instagram and Tiktok reels, even Instagram reels, in terms of button positions, take priority over posting photos. Optimizing and Creating Video Tiktok and Instagram as a sales marketing social media for advertising and sales promotion is something new in the online grocery world, so this can be a big potential to increase brand awareness and then purchase intention from Inagri. Tiktok and Instagram can also increase the talent possessed by Inagri employees themselves in promoting products with their advertisements. Tiktok and Instagram content can be made routine every week so that it continues to create opportunities to get high attention from the public social media. Moreover, tiktok has a market that is still very wide and open to those who do business in it. Inagri can use this to maximize product sales.
- Participating in marketing events to raise brand awareness for Inagri's Innovation (ST1)
Apart from doing business online, Inagri must also be able to share its business offline through participation in marketing events such as product exhibitions, discussion events about business, participating in SMEs or start-up events held, participating in events from the ministry of agriculture. So that Inagri can increase its brand awareness and is also under great pressure to be able to collaborate with influencers or other companies. Inagri can also take part in exhibitions which are usually held by the West Java government at Gedung Sate as an effort to increase brand awareness and then purchase intention from the people attending the event.
- Improving the quality of human resource by taking courses on Digital Marketing (WT2)
Based on the root cause analysis in chapter 1 which the author explores, one of the causes is the lack of knowledge of Inagri's human resources with optimizing digital marketing for B2C. By improving the quality of Human Resource by participating in Digital Marketing courses, Inagri's Human Resource skills will also increase and can further optimize existing business processes at Inagri. One of the ways is that Inagri can work together with belajarlagihq (online bootcamp) specifically to discuss digital marketing.

CONCLUSION

Inagri is a company that was founded in October 2017 in the city of Bandung. Inagri focuses on Agriculture Technology and Livestock. PT Insan Agritama Teknologi continues to strive to develop its business with several strategic business areas that are mutually integrated with one another. Inagri is a platform that focuses on agriculture that helps farmers and ranchers to find markets and to grow together with a sustainable agribusiness ecosystem system with the help of technology. Inagri's sales have not been consistent in a number of months. Then there was a significant decline of 3.05% from April to May 2021, and there was another decline of 2.12% from July to August. The decline in sales that occurred significantly became a business problem and affected the progress of the company. They only experience very strong sales in March and July 2021, and in other months they struggle to meet their sales goals. The Variables previously tested using PLS-SEM in Chapter 4 have an effect on Brand Awareness, as shown by the following results: Advertising has a positive and significant influence on brand awareness with a p value of 0.000. Respondents perceive that advertising can affect brand awareness at Inagri. Brand Awareness has a positive and significant influence on Purchase Intention with a p value of 0.000. Respondents perceive that advertising can affect Purchase Intention at Inagri. Brand Interactivity has a positive and significant influence on Brand Awareness with a p value of 0.000. Respondents perceive Brand Interactivity can affect Brand Awareness at Inagri. Content Quality has no significant influence on Brand Awareness with a p value of 0.926. Respondents perceive that Content Quality has no affect Brand Awareness at Inagri. Sales Promotion has a positive and significant influence on Brand Awareness with a p value of 0.003. Respondents perceive that Sales Promotion can affect Brand Awareness at Inagri. Based on the SWOT Analysis that has been carried out and previously through the External analysis and Internal analysis processes, the results of the TOWS matrix are carried out with the 5 strategies selected for the proposed marketing strategies. Inagri has proposed the following marketing strategy for implementation: Give Promotion product with brand interactivity and creative advertising, Collaborate with Influencer to promote Inagri, Optimizing and Creating Video Tiktok and Instagram as a sales marketing social media for advertising and sales promotion, Participating in marketing events to raise brand awareness for Inagri's Innovation, Improving the quality of human resource by taking courses on Digital Marketing.

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